

A Study of Caste Dynamics in Bihar: Casting and Casting Out

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Abstract: *Casting* and *Casting Out* have been two major phenomena that could be studied under caste dynamics. Both are opposite in nature, however, have a certain major influence on daily to daily social transactions. Casting out results in a member of a society losing membership what has been referred as a *Jatkat* in local vernaculars. It also sometimes symbolizes fallen in status, prestige, and exclusion. Both these processes are centuries old. Casting may symbolize with common rules, practices, territory, endogamy, and solidarity. Main reasons for a *casting out* to be the defiance of rules by any member of the society or family especially inter caste and inter religious marriages. Most of the castes in Bihar, followed certain customary rules and any deviance is ascertained by the collective decision of the majority. There are methods of creating majority and imposing punishments. In some cases punishment could be extremely harsh that can put life and property in dangers.

Key words: *Caste Dynamics; Casting; Casting Out; Caste Dynamics in Bihar.*

Introduction:

The caste system in India has been one of the significant and most relevant social system in many parts of India. In Bihar, it acquired certain special dimension that attracted several scholars and sociologists. In general a caste system is marked by solidarity, endogamy, and hierarchy, sharing a common profession, territory and culture. Caste certainly has certain ethnic and biological ingredients also. A caste does matter a lot for marriage, voting, religious and cultural practices.

Out of caste marriages are resulted due to people of different castes traditionally living aloof and apart were allowed to come closer and interact mutually due to democratization, urbanization, and Society largely affected the manner social institutions functioned in a particular society, therefore this research expedited the explanatory possibilities of dynamics between the society, its institutions and their consequences. The controls imposed through social institutions such as state, economy, education, and religion created impacts over the rigid caste system. Consecutively there are erosion or compromises over several features of caste systems such as ethnicity, hierarchy, and endogamy. Out of caste marriages is present as an undercurrent or the dynamics within all social groups or castes in India, however that is most visible or reported in urban areas. However, the rigid patriarchy and caste system still not sanctioning all those marriages, especially in rural areas have caused out casting whereby married couples and their children lost their caste identity and labelled as out castes.

If out of caste marriages are on the rise, not sanctioned by the majority of the caste ultimately number of out caste people have increased. In many cases out of caste or religion marriages if not sanctioned, by the majority of the society nevertheless they sanctioned by family members and always be the state. In fact, those families totally lost their caste identities and they marry and remarry without considering caste as a criterion of marriage. Interreligious marriages also taking place on this pattern. Religion changes easily, however; caste does not because it is by birth. The manner a particular caste assigned to children born out of inter caste marriages would be a matter of great interest for social scientists. If the functioning of several social institutions paved way for more and more out of caste marriages, not accepted by the majority and total rejection in rural areas, and definitely created a situation that could refer as *Casting Out*. In this manner, social institutions

functioned in both directions, one sanctioned out of caste marriages while others rejected them, totally or partially and put restrictions and controls.

Caste identity in India comes first to all other identities, including provincial, nationality, region, lingual, cultural, or religious. The characteristics of caste are determined by birth and they obeyed certain rules, regulations concerning food, and engaged in definite occupation. They mostly remained an endogamous group and constructed rules concerning the status and touch ability.

Out castes could be a distinct social problem in India that could have different perspectives in different castes and rural and urban areas. In rural areas, out castes resulted due to not obeying certain rules of the caste and disobeying the authority to enforce rules. However, in urban areas out castes mainly resulted due to out of caste and religion marriages that not sanctioned by the larger society. It could also say that since out of caste, marriages most often harshly dealt in rural areas, despite certain legal provisions therefore such practices were very rare in villages. However, in rural areas certain casual or regular deviant behavior also promoted out casting. Out castes could refer as a social group detached, put into exile, seized to be a member of any particular social group, and excluded. Out castes thoroughly existed within a particular social group, association, or organization and regulated through different primary and secondary social institutions. There have varied reasons for origin of out castes in India since ancient period. Out castes largely resulted due to marital and sexual relationships between persons of different social strata.

Under the premises of a rigid caste system out castes existed in numbers especially in urban areas. The process of urbanization has brought several castes close to each other in urban settings and due to vicinity, love, dowry, and other factors out of caste marriages took place. Out castes identified easily in rural settings, intermingled and not easily identified in the urban settings.

Certain features of caste systems such as ethnicity, heredity, hierarchy, and endogamy could seize due to out casting. Out casting resulted mainly due to Out of caste or Out of religious marriages however there could be several other factors also such as deviance behavior, diseases, bigamy, polygamy, instinctual behavior, foreign visits- immigration, criminal acts, non-respect of the institutions, failed anticipated response and action, homosexuality, incest, family feud etc. Out castes could see resulting due to

imposition of norms and values by different social institutions especially majority of a particular community deciding unfavorably.

Sociologically, an outcast could be a person that made to suffer with social stigma or untouchability, total or partial rejection from home or society or that may term as socially excluded, exiled, or ignored. Caste and outcast are an ancient tradition in India as most of the castes originated due to Outcaste over the centuries. Sometimes several outcaste social groups formed a caste of their own and this provided them the stability of status, power, and they also selected roles in the larger society.

Objectives:

This study was aimed to expedite various explanatory sociological perspectives of out casting. Outcastes have different perspectives, modalities, and orientation in urban and rural contexts. Therefore, this study analyzed the extent and pattern of out casting in India in order to understand the determinants of out casting as well as the functioning of different social institutions and their impacts over the caste system in rural and urban settings. The out castes could be a social problem that required attention by the sociologists in modern contexts for studying outcastes, their social mobility, and stratification. In addition, it was also needed to study the relationships of out castes with various social groups, associations, and institutions. It was expected that the study would be significantly contributing to the existing sources on caste, out castes, social institutions, and control dynamics.

Statement of the problem

Caste dynamics have been more studied in terms of politics, however, it still needed to be studied amidst certain sociological and economical premises. The manner a particular caste organizes its social interactions both within and outside the caste has not been properly studied. Even a selection of a profession or an economic activity required quantification. The question remained answers that why people preferred to vote and marry within the caste and what are those factors that promoted a person to defy caste rules.

There is a lack of information about the reasons people chose to marry of their respective castes. Even the various features of a casting and casting out has not been reported properly because each caste has different systems to regulate their caste affairs.

Bihar is synonymous with the caste politics and it is very much part of daily to daily social transactions. People used to identify and recognize an individual by caste or tend to do so.

In general, several sociologists have outlined out castes as untouchables or a social group fallen in status. In India, there has been a problem of ancient Hindu apartheid that not so presented. Out castes in modern days could no way term as those ethnic, racial, and cultural apartheid nevertheless the problem existed among the modern society in India among both rural and urban areas. The caste system is under tremendous stress due to casting out and not allowing the entry of children in any particular caste because born out of inter caste marriages. The situation

could emerge as a major social problem and demanded assessment, measurement and dedicated studies. It could cause tremendous social unrest and conflicts in the future. Caste and outcastes always remained two major social groups in the entire course of Indian history.

Several misconceptions existed even among literate people about caste, class, Varna, and the gotra system in India because of different versions available difficult to pick any one. One of the problems associated with out of caste marriages has been associated with children that made to face social stigma without having any choice. Although the term out caste could not be synonymous with untouchables or *Achut however*; it could locally referred as *Jatkat* that used to be a matter of great abuse or discrimination.

Out castes existed in India since ancient period, however, not studied accordingly to the modern sociological methods and customs. There is tremendous data gap about the sociology and physiology of the out castes in India. Out of caste, marriages are often crippled with unique challenges that are actually associated with maintaining barriers. Experts claim that it is a natural tendency of people to create barriers in their minds and around them. The problem is about security, preservation, and protection of the society. Society nurtured in such a way to enclose humanity within particular boundaries, limits and observations, and right from birth to the entire course of socialization. Therefore, there are certain things that are intrinsic to this problem and that becoming difficult to deal.

Out of caste marriages, face big hurdles in the light of their decision to defy all and may be the basic norms of society. Out of caste marriage usually subjected to face problems in adapting to a new environment, culture, and rituals. In many societies out of caste, marriages considered a serious deviance and costs life. The discord created between the two families and couple could take any adverse course any time.

It is not so that out casting only existed within a caste system or resulted due to inter caste marriages, however, that also existed within different other social groups such as class, ethnicity, races, languages, religion, professions, nationality, race, and regional. There has been a tremendous struggle between patriarchy, caste system, social institutions, and individuals of different social groups that required study.

There has been a lack of data, the manner caste dynamics work in Bihar. In addition, there were no informational or literatures in Bihar are regarding the two sociological phenomenon castes and out of castes. Both are significant ingredients of the caste dynamics.

Overview of literatures:

J. Sekhon describes in her book about the modern state shaping the society along with other issues such as the history of the country, its religions, its social stratification system, its economic status and role in the global economy, gender relations, its political institutes, and social changes that have taken place in India (Sekhon, 2000). She further explained how religion, economics, and politics play a role in shaping the stratification system of India.

L. Dumont tried to define *caste* and explain the necessity and undeniable need to have the caste system in relation to Hinduism in India. He also explains the caste system and the role it plays in the division of labor in the Indian society (Dumont, 1970).

A. Ostor, L. Fruzzetti, and S. Barnett in their book highlighted the plights of the "Untouchable" (Ostor, 1982).

Andre Béteille in his book provided details on the physical structure of the village in India and highlighted the economic organization of the caste system and social class. He also provided an overview on the distributions of power within the caste system (Béteille, 1965).

G. S. Ghurye in his book *Caste and Race in India*, described politics playing a huge role in the shaping of caste (Ghurye, 1969).

J.H Hutton in his book *Caste in India: Its Nature, Function, and Origins*. Detailed caste structure, its sanctions, and endogamous characters.

R.K Lahiri, in his book *Caste System in Hinduism* provided an account of various characteristics and criteria of different caste and their important roles in society. He also described classifications of caste in terms of occupation, marriage, and discrimination. The book further described the origins of the caste system (Lahiri, 2005). In ancient texts, we could find terms such as *Varnashankars*, *Chandals*, and *Malechhs* and in modern sociology, they could be referred as out castes.

There were several other literatures and studies about the inter caste or inter religious marriages in India, however, most of them were silent over the problems of casting out. *C.T Kannan* studied 149 inter-caste marriages in the city of Bombay and found that inter-caste marriage is steadily increasing (Kannan, 1963). Another study on inter-caste marriage by *Reddy* showed that the scheduled caste exhibited the highest tendency for inter-caste marriages than the other castes (Reddy, 1984). He also found that urban residence could be a reason for inter caste marriages. *K.M Kapadia*, in a study of inter-caste marriages in India, interviewed 513 university graduates and found that 51 percent parents expressed their willingness to cheer children marrying outside their own caste and only one-third were against this departure from custom (Kapadia, 1958). *K. Saroja* found that at higher level of study, especially at postgraduate level students were moderately in favor of inter-caste marriage (Saroja, 1999). *N. Prasad* in his study found that urbanization and industrialization had a certain effect on braking down the barriers of caste (Prasad, 1957). Almost similar viewpoints expressed by *Banerjee* after a study of a social group in Kolkata (Banerjee, 1978).

Research questions of hypothesis

1. What are the common causes, consequences, and problems of out of caste marriages?
2. What are the characteristics of out caste marriages in different settings such as rural-urban, rich-poor, high caste-low caste, and class divide?
3. What are generational and intergenerational features of out of caste marriages and out casting?

Research methodology

An intergenerational survey of out of caste marriages in the urban Patna district was conducted during March 2014 to July 2014. It's expected that in India almost 6.14 percent of total marriages were performed out of caste (Das, 2009). A data of out of caste marriages for the last 10 years was obtained from the district registrar for marriages at Patna. Such data provided name, address, caste, and religion. A generational and an intergenerational survey of selected population conducted taking care of the fact that all classes of people including socially and economically get included appropriately.

Information about caste and religion of the husband and wife also collected. The information collected on caste grouped into four categories, namely Scheduled Tribe (ST), Scheduled Caste (SC), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and Upper castes.

Both bivariate and multivariate analysis used for the analysis. In order to examine effects of socio-economic factors on out casting and out castes, logistic regression analysis carried out in which dependent variable was out castes and independent variables included:- caste, caste category, age, residence, income level before and after marriage, income of families before and after marriage, education, religion, working status, household structure, standard of living and mass media exposure, number of children, years of marriage, separation-desertion or divorce.

Findings

While studying the data of registered marriages in Patna, the foremost observation was that most of the marriages registered with the registrar of marriages at Patna were either performed out of the caste or religion. However, in some marriages taking place within a particular caste were also registered however, most of such cases they were performed without the consent and sanction of respective families or even in some cases consent of one family was taken while counterpart family was missing. There were numerous cases whereby most of the witnesses were none of the family member, however, either friends of any of the couples getting married.

On the one side there was a hard caste system on the other side there was a liberal urban ecosystem which either tolerated such marriages or did not bother at all. Most of such marriages faced criminal cases lodged by either or both of the families. Even if they were facing difficulties in getting premises on rent.

The worst social problem is witnessed in the rural areas where such couple is totally boycotted. In some cases their property in the rural areas was captured or abandoned, even families of such members residing in villages were taunted and even tortured. In many cases ultimately even it became impossible for such families live peacefully in their native villages and they made to migrate to any safe or unknown places.

One of the major social problems occurred with the children born of such out of caste and out of religion marriages. They are usually not accepted by any of the caste belonged to their parents. Although modern constitutional and legal provisions protected the interest and rights of such couples.

Outcastes in rural and urban areas resulted in different reasons. In urban areas outcastes were those marrying out of their castes and their children while in rural areas outcastes existed due to certain imposition of control or disciplinary action against a particular member of the family of the caste or social groups. Outcastes in rural areas could return to their original castes after some period or removal of sanctions by the larger caste societies, however, in urban areas, it's become very difficult for them to get a reentry into their original castes. In this manner, out casting in urban areas is a permanent phenomenon.

During the survey of almost 138 out of caste marriages, we find no any single evidence that any kind of reentry was possible into their original caste through any means. Although some talks about the caste of father would be the basis of determination of the caste of the children due to a patrilineal system in practice, however, mere writing or mentioning father's caste as their caste reentry into the bigger caste set was never possible for and they remained outcastes as possible.

Caste dynamics have two distinct features *casting* and *casting out*. Casting has created, sustained, and promoted various castes of Bihar whereas out casting leads to disorganization of a caste. In addition, *casting* leads to coexistence, sharing of common territory and practices, endogamy and solidarity. Both *casting* and *casting out* has remained present in the Indian social history or the history of caste. Castes are organized, disorganized, and reorganized. This has been a continuous phenomenon in Indian social life. Caste would be losing its static and constant entity. It is generally affected by out of the caste marriages. However, out of caste marriages have affected the stability of the original castes of the two persons mutually getting married. Children born of such marriages in general are not accepted by any of the two castes. They, however, due to certain governmental provisions continue to mention the caste of either of the mother or father as their caste. However, it would be always controversial to decide a caste of the caste of a child born out any inter caste or inter religious marriages.

The study has revealed that there were three major concerns that promoted casting and it was to protect, the specific biology, economy, solidarity, culture, and philosophy. People who were not willing to lose their biological features promoted and patronized the caste system.

The study has found that there were some specific and mixed reason for preferring an out of caste marriage. Such reasons varied from individual to individual and mainly individual situations and preferences were the main reason. It was found that younger children of a family majorly performed inter caste or inter religious marriages. In some cases gender issues also played significant role whereby any girl belonging to upper caste getting married to any backward or dalit caste individual mainly to satisfy their femininity of having an upper hand. Many families were due to financial limitations were not able to find a suitable

girl and a boy within their own caste. Even due to proximity of habitation, especially in urban settings girls and boys usually came in mutual contact and became a mutual lover leading to marriage. In some cases due to pre-marital sexual affairs, girl getting pregnant, leaving behind no choice for undergoing inter caste or inter religious marriage.

Conclusion

Despite the two apposite caste dynamics such as casting and casting out working simultaneously there were certain signs that caste system is eroding either slowly or moderately. Inter caste or inter religious marriages are being accepted by rich and progressive people. Such marriages are taking place across all castes and religions. However, it is more apparent in those castes which have either no or nominal linkages with rural areas or their native villages. The numbers of out castes are increasing day to day. The future of a caste is at stake. However, still some rich, urban, and influential class can afford it. People from rural and economically vulnerable sections of society still bound to face difficulties.

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